

Effect of some organic compounds on the mobility of some trace metals through soil amended with fly ash

Samiullah Khan^a, Jamal A. Khan^b, R. K. Bhardwaj^a and Shagufta Jabin^{a*}

^aDepartment of Applied Chemistry, Z. H. College of Engineering & Technology, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 002, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 002, India

Manuscript received 8 June 1999, revised 21 February 2000, accepted 3 March 2000

The effects of some organic compounds, viz. formic acid, acetic acid, methanol, ethanol, formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, acetone and ethyl methyl ketone on the mobility of some trace metals, viz. Co, Zn, Cu, Ag and Pb through soil amended with fly ash have been investigated in an alkaline fine sandy loam soil of Aligarh district (U.P.). The results indicate decrease in the mobility of trace metals with increasing dosage of fly ash in soil but with a variation in intensity by use of organic compound as a mobile phase. The mobility order is Co > Zn > Cu > Ag > Pb in case of organic acids and alcohols, and Co > Cu > Zn > Ag > Pb for aldehydes and ketones. The effect of organic chemicals on the translocation of metals follows the sequence : formic acid > acetic acid > methanol > acetone > formaldehyde > ethyl methyl ketone > acetaldehyde > ethanol.

Various synthetic, volatile and non-volatile organic chemicals are released in the environment from the industries and chemical laboratories in appreciable quantities. It has also been revealed in literature that several organic compounds such as aldehydes, ketones, carboxylic acids, etc. are produced in soil as a result of chemical¹ or biochemical² decomposition of organic matter used in agriculture and of the crop residues. They are found to play an important role in the translocation of plant nutrients as well as toxic metals and their availability³ to plants. Higher dosages of these organic chemicals sometimes become fatal to plants and adversely affect the life processes of soil microorganism.

Among trace metals Zn, Cu and Co are regarded as micronutrients and are required for the healthy growth of plants and animals. Zn^{II} acts as a prosthetic group of an enzyme in the conversion of tryptophan into indole acetic acid, the growth promoting hormone. Copper is required in certain biological oxidation-reduction systems, whereas cobalt is regarded to be essential for symbiotic N₂ fixation by some microorganism and in the synthesis of vitamin B₁₂ needed for animal health. Silver and lead⁴ are hazardous for plants, microflora and soil microorganism⁵.

The use of fly ash as a source of plant nutrients tried in agriculture has become topic of research⁶. However, scanty information is available in literature on the role of fly ash in the translocation of trace metals through soil amended with it in relation of these soil organics. The present study was designed with a view to ascertain the role of certain organic compounds, namely, acetic acid, formic acid,

ethanol, methanol, acetaldehyde, formaldehyde, acetone and ethyl methyl ketone on the translocation of some trace metals such as Co, Zn, Cu, Ag and Pb through soil amended with fly ash.

Results and Discussion

It is evident from Fig. 1 that mobility of trace metals, namely, Co, Zn, Cu, Ag and Pb varies with varying concentration of fly ash in soil as well as with the nature of organic compounds used as mobile phase. The mobility of various metal ions follows the order : Co > Zn > Cu > Ag > Pb, through soil amended with fly ash as a static phase and water or given organic acids and alcohols used as mobile phase. These results are in close agreements with the work of Gaszczyk *et al.*⁷. This order of mobility seems to be inversely related to the order of their binding capacity of given ions with the soil colloids⁸. The mobility order of metal ions in case of aldehydes and ketones follows the order : Co > Cu > Zn > Ag > Pb, which is slightly different from the above. The variation in the order of mobilities between copper and zinc in the systems of acids and alcohols on one hand and in aldehydes and ketones on the other may be attributed to the difference in the rate of their permeability and nature of functional groups present in the mobile phases of these systems. The mobility is found to decrease with the increasing dosages of fly ash in soil and is attributed to the enhancement in the adsorbing capacity caused by the unburnt carbon content (0.6%) in fly ash⁹.

The order of organic compounds in the translocation of trace metals through soils is governed by their chemical be-

Fig. 1. Mobility of trace metals as affected by some organic compounds through soil amended with fly ash
(O) Co, (●) Zn, (Δ) Cu, (×) Ag, (*) Pb

behaviour in soils. These organic compounds indicate the mobility order in the various soil systems as formic acid > acetic acid > methanol > formaldehyde > ethyl methyl ketone > acetaldehyde > ethanol. The highest mobility in case of formic acid and acetic acid seems to be governed by their ionizing as well as solubilizing tendencies as revealed by their inverse order of pK_a values. However, in case of alcohols, the mobility of metal ions is governed by the molecular size and the capability of forming the hydrogen bond with the hydrated metal ions in soil of pH 8.4. Thus the metal ions move in the order :

which is the reverse sequence of the molecular weight of the given alcohols.

The mobility of metal ions in case of organic com-

pounds containing carbonyl groups follows the order acetone > formaldehyde > ethyl methyl ketone > acetaldehyde. The order of mobility seems to be governed by polarity of these compounds in soils. The carbonyl compounds containing alkyl groups capable of imposing steric hindrance also play a decisive role in determining the affinity of interaction of metal ions with these organic compounds used as mobile phase. For example, in case of ketones, the mobility of metal ions is higher in acetone than in ethyl methyl ketone since the carbonyl group in acetone is sterically less hindered as compared to ethyl methyl ketone. Similarly, in aldehydes, the mobility of metal ions in formaldehyde is more as compared to acetaldehyde due to the steric hindrance posed by the one methyl group attached over the carbonyl group of acetaldehyde.

Experimental

The soil used was an 'aeric Halaquept' (fine sandy loam) collected from Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh (U.P.). The physicochemical properties of the soil and fly ash were : soil : sand 60%, silt 26%, clay 14%, organic

matter¹⁰ 0.45%, pH 8.4 (1 : 2.5, soil : water), E.C. 0.167 mmho cm⁻¹, CEC 16.3 cmol (p⁺) kg⁻¹ soil, exchangeable Na⁺ 1.0, K⁺ 0.5, Ca²⁺ 3.5 and Mg²⁺ 1.2 cmol (p⁺) kg⁻¹; fly ash : pH 6.65 (1 : 2.5 FA : water ratio), E.C. 0.71 mmho cm⁻¹, available NH₄⁺-N 30.4, NO₃⁻-N 24.80, NO₂⁻-N 3.20, P 470 and K 198.4 mg kg⁻¹ fly ash (determined by the method used in soil analysis)¹¹.

The soil sample was dried, ground and then passed through a 100 mesh sieve¹² to make it homogenous. Fly ash was added to the soil at the rate of 0, 2.5, 5.0, 7.5, 10.0, 12.5 g/kg soil. It was then thoroughly mixed so as to get a homogenous mixture in each case. The slurry of the amended soil was then prepared in distilled water and coated on glass plates with a uniform layer of 0.5 mm thickness in each case. The plates were then air-dried at room temperature (30 ± 3°). Two lines were drawn at 4 and 14 cm from the base on the plate so as to allow developer to run a distance of 10 cm for the study. An aqueous solution of Co, Zn, Cu, Ag and Pb nitrate (0.01 M) were spotted on the base line. The plates were wrapped with the wet filter paper at the bottom and developed by ascending chromatography in closed TLC¹³ chamber using distilled water and aqueous solution (0.25 M) of organic compounds, viz. formic acid, acetic acid, methanol, ethanol, formaldehyde, acetaldehyde, acetone and ethyl methyl ketone as a developer. The developed plates were air-dried at 60° and spots were detected by spraying 0.1 (w/v) ethanolic solution of haematoxylin that gave stable violet spots for Co²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, Pb²⁺ and red for Ag⁺ and the R_f values evaluated.

References

1. F. E. Allison, "Soil Organic Metal and its Role in Crop Produc-

tion", Elsevier, New York, 1973.

2. D. T. Gibson and M. Decker, "Microbial Degradation of Organic Compounds", Academic, New York, 1984; I. Artsukeich and Z. Solaman, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1997, 127, 921
3. J. P. Singhal, S. U. Khan and S. Nandan, *Indian J Agric Sci.*, 1979, 49, 423.
4. S. U. Khan and N. N. Khan, *Plant Soil*, 1983, 74, 387; F. A. Bazaz, R. W. Carlson and G. L. Rolfe, *Environ. Pollut.*, 1974, 7, 241; D. C. Gupta, G. Singh, R. N. Saxena and K. C. Amarjeet, *Environ Media*, 1998, 3, 257; W. H. Smith, *Environ Pollut.*, 1974, 6, 111, S. U. Khan, D. Nandan and N. N. Khan, *Environ. Pollut.*, 1982, 4, 119.
5. P. C. Brook and S. P. McGrath, *J. Soil Sci.*, 1984, 35, 341, P. C. Brook, S. P. McGrath, D. A. Klein and E. T. Elliot, "Environmental Contamination", CEP Ltd., Edinburgh, 1984.
6. S. U. Khan, T. Begum and J. Singh, *Indian J. Environ. Hlth.*, 1996, 38, 41; C. O. Plank, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1974, 81, 250; Andojumpei, N. Jungi, Uzawa, Nagano and Yoji, *Nippon Dojo Hiryogaku Zasshi*, 1986, 57, 391 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, 107, 620); A. Majumdar and S. N. Mukherjee, *Fuel Sci. Technol.*, 1983, 2, 80; L. C. Mishra and K. N. Shukla, *Environ Pollut., Ser. A*, 1986, 41, 1
7. Gaszczyk, Pyszark and Paszko, *Environ. Sci. Res.*, 1996, 51, 329.
8. F. G. Stevenson and M. S. Ardakani, "Micronutrients in Agriculture", Soil Sci. Soc. of America, Madison, 1972; L. J. Lund, A. L. Page and C. O. Nelson, *J. Environ. Qual.*, 1976, 5, 330.
9. A. K. Sen and A. K. De, *Wat. Res.*, 1987, 21, 885; *Indian J Technol.*, 1987, 25, 259.
10. A. Walkley and C. A. Black, *Soil Sci.*, 1947, 63, 251.
11. M. L. Jackson, "Soil Chemical Analysis", Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, 1958.
12. S. U. Khan, M. A. Qureshi and J. Singh, *J. Environ. Hlth.*, 1997, 39, 217.
13. S. U. Khan, N. N. Khan and N. Iqbal, *Environ. Pollut.*, 1991, 70, 109.